

Application of Artificial Based Intelligent Robot in Library & Information Services

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Abstract: *The fields of robotics and artificial intelligence are developing quickly, with new developments occurring daily as these technologies offer a glimpse into the future of automation and human-computer interaction. Overall, the future of humanity is greatly enhanced by the development of robotics and AI. Although these technologies are still in their infancy, as researchers continue to investigate their potential applications, we'll probably see even more breakthroughs in the years to come. With a focus on "robots," this study clarifies how artificial intelligence (AI) might be efficiently applied in libraries. Several tasks that can be performed by robots in the library include book arrangement, sorting, retrieval, material handling, inventory, etc. In India, the technology is still in its infancy but will eventually get the necessary pace in the coming days. It would be useful to understand how AI technology can be included to help different library activities after reading this paper.*

Keywords: Robots, Robotics, Robotics Libraries, Artificial Intelligence

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) & automated robots are currently emerging as part of the 4th industrial revolution (Xu et al., 2018). AI utilizes the area of computer science that emphasizes basically the creation of intelligent machines that work & reacts like humans. As per Merriam Webster dictionary, Artificial Intelligence is ‘a branch of computer science dealing with the simulation of intelligent behaviour in computers.

The entire landscape of industry & education is being disrupted by this transformation of AI as well as automated robots. We can see different types of industries around the world, where humanoid service robots are in use.

However, it is now being investigated how these humanoid robots might be incorporated into the library industry as well as any potential, ethical, privacy, & legal consequences. High-intelligence humanoid robots may encounter ethical & moral dilemmas, according to some scientists. Other things to think about are how humans & robots may coexist in the same environment.

AI, robotics & Libraries

The creation of intelligent computer programmes that mimic different facets of intelligent human conduct is the focus of AI research. According to Amit (2018), the focus has been on modelling the knowledge structures employed in human problem solving. AI is the modelling of human cognitive processes by computer systems. Examples of these processes include learning (the acquisition of knowledge & the rules for applying it) & reasoning (which includes the rules to arrive at approximations or firm conclusions & self-correction).

Applications of AI include expert systems, speech recognition, search and optimization, fuzzy system, Natural Language Processing (NLP) & knowledge representation, machine vision, machine learning and probabilistic reasoning, planning and decision making & neural works. An Expert System's applications in libraries is to help the librarian in realizing the need for better improvement in the library operations and services. The Expert System works as a substitute for a reference librarian i.e. Ask Librarian. So, AI represents a paradigm shift in the way humans think & act (Wong et al., 2020). AI is utilised in a variety of the military, the medical field, business, education and gaming. AI & game systems for libraries were originally suggested in 1990. Descriptive cataloguing, subject indexing, reference services, and technical services are all areas where artificial intelligence is used in library systems; systems for information retrieval, collection creation, and shelf reading. Many libraries are automating their processes to increase efficiency (Duan et al., 2019).

Robotics design, development, use, and application are also topics covered by AI (Abram, 2019). In essence, a robot is a machine that can perform a complex series of tasks autonomously under the guidance of a computer programme. There are three components: the mechanical component, the sensor, and the controller. The brain of the robot, which is directed by a computer programme that issues instructions to its moving parts, serves as the controller.

The robot's mechanical components, which enable it to lift, grab, turn, and move, include motors, pistons, grippers, wheels, and gears. The robot can assess size, shape, distance between objects, and orientation thanks to the sensor's information about its environment (Science Trek, 2019). All environments and occupations where manual labour formerly worked have started to be invaded by robots. Tella (2020) stated that robotics and AI, like other disruptive technologies, have fundamentally changed how libraries supply information services. Along with automated information storage and retrieval, libraries have deployed robots for both internal and external operations. Robotics immediately affects libraries as well as the greater informational (and social) environment in which libraries and librarians of all kinds operate (Owolabi et al., 2022). Robotics in libraries frees up librarians' time to concentrate on other crucial information service delivery to today's changing needs. According to Harisanty et al. (2020), some areas where robotic technologies have been integrated into library operations include shelving and finding library materials, security, questions and responding to repetitive reference and directional queries, outreach and public relation (PR) via library tours, and even information illiteracy training. Robotic automated storage and retrieval technologies are also helpful for managing library space (Echedom and Okuonghae, 2021).

Based on the different types of robots and the applications they can be used for; an attempt has been made to categorise them. Following are some instances of robotic services that apply to libraries. Books that are missing or out of order can be found on the shelves using shelf reading robots. Robots can independently scan the print collection after the library shuts by spotting radio frequency identifier (RFID) tags included in the volumes, according to Cox (2021). A self-localization method is used by

shelf-reading robots to analyse the digital data acquired against the library's collection database and find the 5% of the collection's books that are missing or incorrectly shelved. Most notably, it deals with the common consumer gripe of being unable to find a book in the library. The library catalogue is connected with the item locations gathered during the daily scan.

The user interface of a chatbot is typically a website or messaging service that may accept text input and send it on to a layer of natural language processing (NLP) that tries to break down words into entities and the intents of the query.

An NLP layer, which tries to break down phrases into entities and query intents, can take text input from a chatbot, which is more of a user interface, generally a website or messaging platform (Alli, 2019). Following the determination of the intent, a response is produced utilising the pertinent knowledge base and, occasionally, an external Web service for more complicated requests.

The robot can also recognise some individuals, such as library workers. They are conversational, expressive robots that can dance or tell stories. It is a robot that is employed in public libraries to do a variety of tasks, including instructing children and adults in coding and library rules. These machines look like human beings.

For instance, the Roanoke County Public Library is home to a Pepper robot (Jones, 2018). Various forms of library enquiries can be answered by this kind of robot. Students can approach a librarian with a question they might otherwise be too embarrassed to ask thanks to telepresence, which allows them to see one other and communicate visually.

Children can benefit from the use of robots in show-and-tell sessions, coding lessons, and story time. Children with autism, for example, are thought to benefit from interaction with robots (Nguyen, 2019). Kids who are more self-assured are more likely to be attracted to, love, and desire to interact with robots. Because many participants speak a second language and enjoy practising English with the robot, this creates a fresh learning experience.

Concluding Remarks

Robotics and AI undoubtedly have the potential to change the world, giving us more assurance and hope as we navigate a future that is changing quickly. Whether we accept or reject these new technologies, they are unquestionably here to stay and will continue to play a significant role in all of our lives.

Together with their parent institutions or organisations, libraries should create a strategic plan for cutting-edge technology like humanoid robots. Additionally, they ought to collaborate more closely with other parties, like academic institutions and robotics labs staffed by roboticists. Public libraries and local government councils should strengthen their collaborations with robot vendors in order to take advantage of direct support. Open contact between library management boards and librarians is encouraged, particularly when it comes to problems involving humanoid robots.

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